

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

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Disclaimer

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RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity gap in sampling and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. These goals will be achieved by combining state-of-the-art methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy. It will also design new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
DB	Database
EIC	European Innovation Council
EU	European Union
F2SS	Forecasting & Foresight Support System
FSS	Forecasting Support Systems
GIS	Geographical Information System
ML	Machine Learning
POIS2ON	Prototype RAMONES Information System for Socioeconomic stakeholders
RMIS	Risk Management Information System
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
WP	Work Package

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Abstract

RAMONES is an FET H2020 project which achieved high-resolution temporal and spatial underwater AI-driven radioactivity measurements, in situ and in near-real-time, forming a new capability in deep-water environmental monitoring.

RAMONES introduces a new generation of submarine radiation-sensing instruments, assisted by robotic and artificial intelligence solutions towards understanding radiation related risks near and far from coastal areas, while providing data for the international community towards facing better eminent and long-term risks.

One of the main capabilities of RAMONES is to monitor and **inform** socio-political and socio-economic **stakeholders** at various frequencies. To that end, the deliverable **5.8. of Work Package 5 provides the final version of the prototype information system, POIS2ON** (Prototype RAMONES Information System for SocioecONomic stakeholders).

POIS2ON provides statistical and ML forecasts for radionuclide concentrations at high frequency in the sea as well as respective risks. At this final stage full risk awareness capabilities have been integrated to the system via: a) assessing the probability of an instantaneous exposure to radioactivity, as well as: b) connection to the respective UCA database that assesses long-term exposure risks via simulating and calculating absorbed dosages from microorganisms.

Finally, illustrations with real data from deployments of our sensors are also provided in this deliverable.

Keywords

RAMONES; POIS2ON; ML; Forecasting; Radioactivity; Information System; Risk.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

This document belongs to Work Package 5 (WP5, *Citizen Awareness, Communication and Dissemination Activities*), and in particular to Task T5.2 Raising Awareness / Supporting policymaking [M25-M48] - Lead: UDUR with Participants: NKUA, UCA, ENS within which RAMONES provides the **final** version and respective additions to the **POIS2ON** system (D5.1, D5.2, D5.2, D5.4) that has integrated the **RMIS** (D5.5, D5.6, D5.7).

1.2 Structure of the document

From this point, the current document is organized according to the following structure and contents:

Section 2. Final additions to the prototype POIS2ON system

Section 3. Conclusion, Maintenance of the system, and the Future

1.3 Objectives and approach

The objectives of the RAMONES D5.8 deliverable is to deliver the final version of the prototype system **POIS2ON** with all features of the RMIS system and connections to many other systems of RAMONES developed in UCA and NTUA. The approach has been incremental.

2. Final additions to the POIS2ON system

There have been five more developments/additions for POIS2ON during the last (and final) six months of the RAMONES project, since October 2024:

1. The system was transferred permanently to a more robust and secure server within NKUA,
2. The system has been tested with Real data
3. The Risk exposure source code wrote independently in Python in earlier deliverables, has now been written in R and fully integrated in POIS2ON
4. Data are now exchanged with the UCA system in France and visuals can be created in POIS2ON
5. A maintenance plan for POIS2ON post RAMONES has been decided

Addition 1: Secure access to url

There have been some unexpected downtimes during January 2025 of the system and thus a more secure and robust URL and server configuration has been tested and deployed as follows – and since we have no performance issues:

<http://195.134.90.204:8080/Pois2on/>

It can be accessed from anywhere in the world. Current access to POIS2ON at the aforementioned address is done with the following credentials:

Username: Ramones

Password: Gnikol2907

There is also a series of administrative passwords for the system that are held by UDUR and NKUA.

From 1/4/2025 these credentials will become obsolete and new passwords will be provided to potential users only via UDUR or NKUA.

The final POIS2ON system developed with R, R shiny, Python, and MySQL, and is finally running securely in a server within the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens while server administration and maintenance takes place from NKUA and software maintenance from UDUR.

Addition 2: Adding real data to the Risk Forecasting System

The system has been tested with Real data. Real data from the testing of GASPARG in Demokritos [D2025], has been used for testing the system without any issues. The data were inserted via the standard CSV/XLS format and then transferred to the SQL database too. These data running with NN method for the full spectrum measured are visualised in figure 1.

Figure 1 - POIS2ON running with real data.

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 2 we see the operation of POIS2ON with real data and simultaneously with forecasting, visualising also the 3D position (longitude, latitude, depth) of the instrument while taking the measurements.

Figure 2 - POIS2ON running with real data and and3D location visualization

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 3 we see the process for recording the real data for the input file to the SQL database of POIS2ON. The real data of the project – as per the earlier deliverables of POIS2ON are saved either in the nominated repository or in the SQL database of the systems (or both) and necessary for the input to the POIS2ON system is the use of the standard CSV/ XLS file as prescribed in earlier deliverables.

Figure 3 - Saving the real data to DB

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

In figure 4 we see the real data from the measurement of GASPARG for ¹³⁷Cs on 22 November 2024 in Demokritos [D 2025]

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
1	Location	Lon	Lat	Depth	Instrumer	Date	Time	Cs.137	Ra.226	Pb.214	Pu.240	Full_Spectrum	
2	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	600	0.018	0	0	0	0.018	
3	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	1500	84.162	0	0	0	84.162	
4	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	1517	472.118	0	0	0	472.118	
5	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	1817	185.47	0	0	0	185.47	
6	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	2417	6.438	0	0	0	6.438	
7	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	3017	190.757	0	0	0	190.757	
8	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	3617	116.185	0	0	0	116.185	
9	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	4217	126.997	0	0	0	126.997	
10	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	4817	14.952	0	0	0	14.952	
11	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	5417	0.537	0	0	0	0.537	
12	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	6017	17.25	0	0	0	17.25	
13	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	6310	0.317	0	0	0	0.317	
14	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	6910	188.043	0	0	0	188.043	
15	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	7210	315.02	0	0	0	315.02	
16	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	8110	0.017	0	0	0	0.017	
17	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	9010	0.009	0	0	0	0.009	
18	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	9910	0.014	0	0	0	0.014	
19	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	10810	0.007	0	0	0	0.007	
20	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	11710	0.009	0	0	0	0.009	
21	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	12610	0.014	0	0	0	0.014	
22	Demokritos Reactor	23.8212	37.99683		3 Gaspar	22-11-24	13510	0.009	0	0	0	0.009	

Figure 4 - A subset of real data file from the system

Addition 3: Global integration to POIS2ON

The Risk exposure source code wrote independently in Python in earlier deliverables, has now been written in R and fully integrated in POIS2ON.

Figure 5 - Integration of Exposure Risk Estimation in POIS2ON.

In figure 5 we see the integration of the Risk assessment estimation in POIS2ON. With a very friendly User Interface – and only parameter needed being the maximum permissible dose (that can vary among different conditions or recommendations/legislation thus it was made a parameter and not a constant), we do estimate the probability to be exposed to such dosage instantaneously.

This is a dynamic calculation and is based on the errors of the forecasting method selected, and as such every time we forecast with a new method this is recalculated, a distribution is fitted to the errors, and an estimation is made for the chances to reach the parametrised threshold; plus the respective intuitively appealing visualisation is offered.

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

Figure 6 - Calculation of Risk Exposure for High threshold

In figure 6 we see the integration of the Risk assessment estimation in POIS2ON for a High threshold of 1000 resulting in almost 0% chances to be exposed to such quantity.

Repository, Information System and Risk no2

Figure 7 - Calculation of Risk Exposure for Low threshold

In figure 7 we see the integration of the Risk assessment estimation in POIS2ON for a Low threshold of 2 resulting in almost 31% chances to be exposed to such quantity.

Addition 4: On-time evaluation of microdosimetry

POIS2ON can be interfaced with the GATE MARIM database (developed by UCA partner in WP4 and accessible through <https://github.com/lpc-umr6533/marim>) which proposes Dose Conversion Coefficients (DCC) for 15 alpha-emitting isotopes from the ^{238}U and ^{232}Th decay chains, to evaluate the microdosimetry of microscopic species living in environments with different porosity levels. To calculate the dose rates for microorganisms submitted to external exposure to alpha radiation (for example ^{226}Ra), we can use the activity concentrations (in Bq.L^{-1} or Bq.kg^{-1}) measured through the instruments deployed in the environment (see Figure 4 with the databases of radionuclides detected from gamma spectrometry using the GASPARD instrument) and calculate the dose rates (in $\mu\text{Gy.h}^{-1}$) as a function of the activity concentration as plotted in Figure 8.

Figure 8 - Real time connection of POIS2ON with the GATE MARIM database to assess dose rates to microorganisms exposed to external radiation from ²³⁸U and ²³²Th decay chains

Addition 5: Maintenance Improvements

A maintenance plan for POIS2ON post RAMONES has been decided including:

- a) Maintenance of the server from NKUA
- b) Maintenance of the POIS2ON software by UDUR
- c) Deployment of system at a 2-weeks notice

3. Conclusions, Maintenance of the System, Deployment, and the Future

RAMONES introduced novel monitoring and response channels to inform key socio-political and socio-economics stakeholders at regular intervals. To that end, the deliverable **D5.8** of Work Package 5 **provides the final additions** to the prototype information system **POIS2ON**.

POIS2ON provides statistical and ML forecasts for radionuclide concentrations in the sea as well as respective instantaneous (and long-term exposure) risks. Provision for spatial-temporal representation and visualization has been implemented via connections to a GIS system as well as link to a system developed by UCA that simulates and calculates absorbed dosages from microorganisms and humans.

For further dissemination, submission of the POIS2ON architecture and functionality will be done as an academic paper to PLOS ONE and HICSS26 by June 2026.

The system now transitions to maintenance phase post 1/4/2025 and remains **deployable** at a two-weeks' notice wherever it may be needed for public use.

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